

SILKFIBROIN-CA-P COMPOSITE BONE REPLACEMENT MATERIAL FOR GUIDED BONE GROWTH

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ABSTRACT

Mineralized natural protein based materials are investigated as novel materials to be used in tissue engineering and as bone replacement materials. Silk fibroin fiber based foams and films are used as mineralized composites due to their excellent biocompatibility. In this study, the biomimetic mineralization of orderly oriented fibrous silk based scaffolds was studied. Commercially obtained pure silk woven fabric was boiled in 0.02 M Na₂CO₃ for 20 min. The deposition of calcium phosphate was conducted at 37°C for twenty minutes in seven sequential immersion steps in 250 mM CaCl₂ 2H₂O and 120 mM K₂HPO₄, both containing 0.15 M NaCl and 50mM solution of TRIS-HCl, buffered at 7.4. Ca-P deposit on the samples increased with the number of immersion steps. The analysis of the Ca-P powder deposit indicated formation of brushite with its characteristic peak at around 11.76 2θ using the XRD and at 1000, 3000-3500 cm⁻¹ using the FTIR analyses. Samples were sputter coated with gold for SEM characterization. The morphology of the Ca-P deposits confirmed formation of brushite crystals, which were then transformed into HA using electrochemical hydrothermal treatment in concentrated SBF solution 40°C at a current density of -25mA/cm² for 60 min. HA formation was confirmed using XRD, FTIR and SEM analysis. The deposition and electrochemical conversion of brushite to hydroxyapatite on silk, thus forming a silk-HA composite material may be an inexpensive

promising biocompatible graft material to be used in bone replacement surgery, where highly oriented materials for guided cell growth may be needed.

1 INTRODUCTION

As a material that provides motility, stature, protection, blood cell formation, a reservoir for calcium, magnesium and phosphate ions [1]. Bones consist of hydroxyapatite (HAP), Collagen Type I and water forming a hierarchically organized material [2]. Various studies have attempted to biomimick the natural tissues providing a calcium-phosphate (Ca-P) osteoconductive nanostructure which provide adhesion and differentiation of osteoprogenitor cells [3,4]. However, Ca-P biomaterials may not be sufficient for bone repair, therefore, autograft, allograft, xenograft materials as well as alloplastic and synthetic materials may be used for the treatment and augmentation of bone fracture [5]. Traditionally, metal implant materials are used in bone fracture treatment as bone replacement materials [6]. In addition to metals, bone graft materials used in bone fracture treatment offer the surgeon an abundant, yet expensive source of bone replacement materials, which may have inadequate size and shape. Therefore, there is a need for synthetic bone replacement agents, i.e. polymeric and ceramic materials, with supplementary elements [7].

Osteobiological biomaterials currently used in tissue engineering consist of a scaffold with growth factors and cells. The osteoconductive scaffold with adequate pore size and total porosity enables both anchorage of cells and facilitation of nutrients and metabolites [8]. More commonly used biodegradable synthetic polymers are polyglycolic acid (PGA), polylactic acid (PLA), and copolymers of poly-DL-lactic-glycolic acid (PLGA), as well as biodegradable naturally derived polymers such collagen, fibrin [9] and silk [10]. Comparing these polymers, silk protein may be favoured due to its very slow degradation, non-crosslinking chemical stabilization and high open porosity promoting a homogenous growth of cells [11]. With enhanced mechanical properties, biocompatibility and biodegradability, silk-based biomaterials may have extensive use in biomedical applications [12-14]. In addition, silk is a material that can withstand high temperatures and severe conditions.

For cellular growth into the scaffold and prevention of formation of necrotic zones, silk-fibroin scaffolds for bone tissue engineering have proven to demonstrate the appropriate chemistry, morphology and structure, enabling adhesion and differentiation of osteoblasts and osteoprogenitor cells [8]. Three-dimensional porous silk fibroin scaffolds may be prepared using aqueous [10] and organic solvent-based process [15], controlling the porosity, pore size and mechanical properties through the manipulation of silk fibroin protein concentration and the porogen size [10,15]. Osteoinductive effect of the silk-fibroin based bone replacement materials may be improved by deposition of HAP on the material using biomimickry to imitate the polymer-mineral features observed in natural bone [16,17]. Deposition of HA or CHA on natural fiber under physiological conditions may be rather difficult [18], requiring the use of expensive polyhydroxy acids [19-21].

In this study, we attempted to use electrochemical methods that have satisfactorily resulted in formation of CHA [18]. The method is economically favourable and practical to use as a C/HA deposition alternative that does not require the use of any growth factors and polyhydroxy acids. Electrochemical incorporation of biological HA into porous biodegradable silk fibroin scaffolds are expected to improve osteogenic outcomes.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Preparation and characterization of silk scaffold:

Commercially obtained pure silk fabric was boiled for 20 min in an aqueous solution of 0.02 M Na_2CO_3 , and then rinsed thoroughly with distilled water to remove the coloring and any textile coating, and characterized using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM).

2.2. Mineralization of silk fabric scaffold:

The silk-fibroin scaffold was then mineralized using a solution of modified simulated body fluid. Following Kim et. al. [16], the silk fibroin scaffolds (5 cm × 3 cm) were immersed in 20 ml of 250 mM $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution (containing 0.15 M NaCl and buffered with 50 mM TRIS·HCl, pH 7.4) for 20 min at 37 °C and transferred to 20 ml of 120 mM Na_2HPO_4 solution (containing 0.15 M NaCl and

buffered with 50 mM TRIS·HCl, pH 7.4) for 20 min at 37°C [16]. After 7 immersion cycles, the mineralized scaffolds were air-dried and characterized as described in Section 2.4.”

2.3. Electrochemical deposition of hydroxyapatite:

Electrochemical deposition of hydroxyapatite was conducted in a typical three-electrode electrochemical cell. The working electrode was the titanium substrate, the reference electrode was a standard silver-silver chloride electrode (Ag/AgCl in saturated KCl) and the counter electrode was platinized stainless steel. The working electrode was bioactivated by immersion in 0.5M NaOH for 2 min at 50°C and rinsed with deionized water. The mineralized silk fibroin sample was tightly attached to the working electrode. Electrochemical deposition was carried out in modified SBF, a mixture of calcium and phosphate solutions given above, at 40°C by maintaining a constant cathodic current density of -25 mA/cm^2 for 60 minutes [22].

2.4. Characterization of mineral deposit:

After the mineralization of silk fabric scaffold and the electrochemical deposition process, dried samples were characterized for crystallinity using a glancing X-Ray Diffractometer (Philips PW 3710), at the grazing angle of 1° , and at the range of scattering angle from 20 up to 60 2θ , at a step size of 0.2 2θ . Silk scaffolds were cut into 1 mm thick slices and sputter coated with gold in order to examine the morphology of the mineral deposited on the scaffolds using the SEM (Zeiss, Evo40). Molecular bonding of the samples was characterized using the FT-IR, scanning at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} over a frequency range of 500–4000 cm^{-1} using the attenuated total reflectance (ATR) technique by FT-IR Spectrometer (Perkin Elmer, Diamond).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the seven sequential immersion cycles, the progress of mineralization was visible to the naked eye. The thickness of the mineral layer increased with each consecutive step of immersion in calcium and phosphate solutions. The initial deposit was a white powder that could be easily crumbled into fine particles.

3.1 Characterization of the mineralized silk scaffold

The XRD analysis of the initial mineral deposit on the samples indicated formation of brushite as can be identified with its distinctive 100% peak appearing at 10.76 2θ (Fig. 1a). SEM imaging of the initial deposit on the samples validated the XRD results, with its distinctive monoclinic crystals (Fig. 2a). The FT-IR analysis of the samples indicated as well, formation of brushite with the distinctive peaks appearing at 1000, 3000-3500 cm^{-1} of the spectrum (Fig. 3a) [23,24].

Figure 1: The XRD spectra of the mineral deposited on the silk scaffold. (a) pre- and (b) post-electrochemical deposition process.

Figure 2: The SEM images of the mineral deposited on the silk scaffold. (a) pre- and (b) post-electrochemical deposition process.

Figure 3: The FT-IR spectrum of the mineral deposited on the silk scaffold. (a) pre- and (b) post-electrochemical deposition process.

3.2 Characterization of the electrochemically deposited mineral on silk scaffold

The XRD analysis of the initial mineral deposit on the samples indicated formation of carbonated hydroxyapatite (CHA) as can be identified with its distinctive 100% peak appearing at 32.18 2 θ as indicated in ICSD 00-019-0272 (Fig. 1b). SEM imaging of the deposit on the samples validated the XRD results, indicating formation of crystals with hydroxyapatite morphology (Fig. 2b). The FT-IR analysis of the samples indicated as well, formation of carbonated hydroxyapatite with the distinctive phosphate peaks appearing at 1000-1200 cm⁻¹, carbonate peaks at 1419, 1454 cm⁻¹ and O-H stretch appearing between 3000-3500 cm⁻¹ of the spectrum (Fig. 3b) [23,24]. The -OH peak that is observed around 3560 cm⁻¹ of the spectrum may have been weakened due to carbonate substitution.

3.3 Electrochemical conversion of brushite to hydroxyapatite

The brushite mineral was successfully deposited on the silk-fibroin scaffold at 37 °C and at physiological pH (Fig. 2a). Brushite is a highly soluble mineral which may not be used in load-bearing sites and materials [17,23,24]. Using electrochemistry, with the provision of electrons at the cathode, both hydrogen phosphate ions and water were reduced to phosphate and hydroxide ions. Comparing the distribution of deposition of both compounds on the silk-fibroin protein, brushite was deposited more homogeneously than CHA, with a less homogenous and thorough distribution. On the contrary, the CHA coating, did not readily crumble to smaller particles as brushite deposit did.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Using the calcium and phosphate sequential immersion steps, brushite was successfully deposited on the silk-fibroin scaffold and converted to carbonated hydroxyapatite using electrochemistry at 37°C at physiological pH. Using the electrochemical deposition method, CHA deposited silk-fibroin material of any shape and size can be prepared effectively and efficiently.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J.D. Currey, *Bones: Structure and Mechanics*, Princeton University Press, Princeton, NJ, 2002.
- [2] F.S. Utku, M. Barak, E. Klein, CA. Yucesoy, H. Saybasili, S. Weiner, Probing the role of water in lamellar bone by dehydration in the Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope, *Journal of Structural Biology*, **162**, 2008, pp. 361-367.
- [3] F.S. Utku, E. Karaca, E. Seckin, G. Goller, M. Urgan, C. Tamerler, The effect of the topographical and chemical properties of titanium implants on osteoblasts, *Proceedings of the National Congress of Medical Technologies 2012, Antalya, Turkey, 2012*.
- [4] J.W.M. Vehof, J. Dolder, E. Ruijter, P.H.M. Spauwen, J.A. Jansen, Bone formation in CaP-coated and noncoated titanium fiber mesh, *J Biomed Mater Res.* **64A**, 2003, pp. 417-26.
- [5] G.J. Meijer, J.D. de Bruijn, R. Koole, C.A van Blitterswijk, Cell-based bone tissue engineering, *PLoS Med.*, **4**, 2007, pp. 260-264.
- [6] T. Kokubo, H.M. Kim, M. Kawashita, T. Nakamura, Bioactive metals: preparation and properties, *J. Mat. Sci. Mater. Med.* **15**, 2004, pp. 99-107.
- [7] R.Z. LeGeros, Properties of osteoconductive biomaterials: calcium phosphates, *Clin Orthop Relat Res.* **395**, 2002, pp. 81-98.
- [8] P.X. Ma, R. Zhang, G. Xiao, R. Franceschi, Engineering new bone tissue in vitro on highly porous poly(α -hydroxy acids)/hydroxyapatite composite scaffolds, *J Biomed Mater Res*, **54**, 2001, pp. 284-93.
- [9] L.B. Rocha, G. Goissis, M.A. Ross, Biocompatibility of anionic collagen matrix as scaffold for bone healing, *Biomaterials*, **23**, 2002, pp. 449-56.
- [10] U.J. Kim, J. Park, H.J. Kim, M. Wada, D.L. Kaplan, Three-dimensional aqueous-derived biomaterial scaffolds from silk fibroin, *Biomaterials*, **26**, 2005, pp. 2775-85.
- [11] Y. Wang, U-J. Kim, D.J. Blasioli, H.J. Kim, D.L. Kaplan, In vitro cartilage tissue engineering with 3D porous aqueous-derived silk scaffolds and mesenchymal stem cells, *Biomaterials*, **26**, 2005, pp. 7082-94.

- [12] S. Sofia, M.B. McCarthy, G. Gronowicz, D.L. Kaplan, Functionalized silk-based biomaterials for bone formation, *J Biomed Mater Res.* **54**, 2001, pp. 139–48.
- [13] G.H. Altman, F. Diaz, C. Jakuba, T. Calabro, R.L. Horan, J. Chen, H. Lu, J. Richmond, D.L. Kaplan, Silk-based biomaterials, *Biomaterials*, **24**, 2003, pp. 401–16.
- [14] B. Panilaitis, G.H. Altman, J. Chen, H.J. Jin, V. Karageorgiou, D.L. Kaplan, Macrophage responses to silk, *Biomaterials*, **24**, 2003, pp. 3079–85.
- [15] R. Nazarov, H.J. Jin, D.L. Kaplan, Porous 3-D scaffolds from regenerated silk fibroin, *Biomacromolecules*, **5**, 2004, pp. 718–26.
- [16] H.J. Kim, U-J. Kim, H.S. Kim, C. Li, M. Wadag, G.G. Leisk, D.L. Kaplan, Bone tissue engineering with premineralized silk scaffolds, *Bone*, **42**, 2008, pp. 1226–1234.
- [17] R.R. Kumar, M. Wang, Biomimetic deposition of hydroxyapatite on brushite single crystals grown by the gel technique, *Materials Letters*, **49**, 2001, pp. 15–19.
- [18] F.S. Utku, E. Seckin, G. Goller, C. Tamerler, M. Urgan, Carbonated Hydroxyapatite deposition at physiological temperature on ordered titanium oxide nanotubes using pulsed electrochemistry, *Ceramics International*, **40**, 2014, pp. 15778-15789.
- [19] L. Addadi, S. Weiner, Interactions between acidic proteins and crystals: stereo-chemical requirements in biomineralization, *Proc Natl Acad Sci*, **82**, 1985, pp. 4110–4.
- [20] R. Zhang, P.X. Ma, Poly(α -hydroxy acids)/hydroxyapatite porous composites for bone-tissue engineering. I. Preparation and morphology, *J Biomed Mater Res.* **44**, 1999, pp. 446–55.
- [21] FS. Utku, E. Yuca, E. Seckin, G. Goller, A. Yazgan-Karatas, M. Urgan, C. Tamerler, Protein-mediated hydroxyapatite composite layer formation on nanotubular titania, *Bioinspired, Biomimetic and Nanobiomaterials*, **4**, 2015, pp. 1–11.
- [22] K.S. Kar, S. Raja, M. Misra, Electrodeposition of hydroxyapatite onto nanotubular TiO₂ for implant applications, *Surf. Coat. Tech.*, **201**, 2006, pp. 3723-3731.
- [23] S. Kannan, F. Goetz-Neunhoffer, J. Neubauer, J.M.F. Ferreira, Ionic substitutions in biphasic hydroxyapatite and β -tricalcium phosphate mixtures: structural analysis by Rietveld refinement, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* **91**, 2008, pp. 1-12.
- [24] I. Rehman, W. Bonfield, Characterization of hydroxyapatite and carbonated apatite by photo acoustic FTIR spectroscopy, *J. Mater. Sci. Mater. Med.*, **8**, 1997, pp. 1-4.